

Gravimetric and Spectrophotometric Determination of Osmium(VI) with N- α -Pyridyl-N-Benzoyl Thiourea (PBT)

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N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea is recommended as an ideal analytical reagent for the determination of osmium(VI) by both gravimetry and spectrophotometry. Osmium(VI) forms a dark green precipitate with the ligand in the pH range 3.1-6.2, which corresponds to the formula $(C_{13}H_{10}N_3OS)_2$. Using proper masking agents, the metal can be gravimetrically separated from all base metals by the use of the reagent.

The green complex of osmium(VI)-N'- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea is extracted quantitatively in the pH range 3.5-5.0 with chloroform in presence of ethanol which shows two maxima, one at 345 nm and the other at 600 nm. It obeys Beer's law at 345 nm over the concentration range of 0.72-2.8 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and also at 650 nm over the concentration range of 5.78-23.04 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of the metal respectively. The colour of the extract is stable for more than 24 hours. The added advantage of this method with the reagent is that, although other platinum and some base metals are extracted with N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea, they exhibit practically no absorption at 650 nm. Hence, osmium(VI) can be determined spectrophotometrically with the reagent at 650 nm in the presence of other platinum metals and all base metals.

ANALYTICAL reagents for precipitation of osmium in directly weighable form are only a few in number. Thionalide¹, 2-phenylbenzothiazole², antipyrine derivatives³, strychnine sulphate⁴ cannot be recommended as precipitants due to the fact that direct weighing of the metal complexes are not feasible. Regarding spectrophotometric determination of osmium, the literature survey reveals no method which permits quantitative determination of the metal in presence of all other platinum metals and base metals commonly associated with osmium. Though Tschugaeeff⁵ introduced thiourea as one of the spectrophotometric reagents for osmium yet it suffers from lack of sensitivity and the method is interfered by various metal ions. Thiosalicylamide (TSA) was recommended by Shome and co-workers⁶ as the spectrophotometric reagent of osmium, but the method was not free from the interferences of other platinum metals. In a previous communication, Shome and co-workers⁷ reported a qualitative study of the use of N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea (PBT) as an analytical reagent for the determination of platinum metals. The present paper deals with the analytical applications of N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea in the gravimetric and spectrophotometric determination of osmium(VI). The reagent offers a reliable method to determine osmium(VI) by forming a dark green complex of directly weighable form which corresponds to $\text{OsO}_2 \cdot (C_{13}H_{10}N_3OS)_2$ within the pH range 3.1-6.2. Osmium is

determined gravimetrically and separated from a large number of base metals with N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea using suitable masking agents.

The dark green precipitate formed by N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea (PBT) with osmium(VI) can be extracted quantitatively with chloroform in presence of ethanol; complete extraction of osmium(VI)-N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea complex takes place in the pH range of 3.5 to 5.0. The green extract shows two maxima, one at 345 nm and the other at 600 nm. Beer's law is obeyed by the extract at 345 nm over the concentration range of 0.72 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ to 2.8 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of the metal and at 650 nm over the concentration range of 5.76 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ to 23.04 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of the metal. The coloured extract is stable for more than 24 hours. The reagent forms coloured complexes with several other metals including platinum metals and the extracts of the complexes have practically no absorption at 650 nm which enables to determine osmium spectrophotometrically with the reagent in presence of all other metals without employing any masking agent.

Experimental

Apparatus: A Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer, PMQ-II model, with 1-cm quartz cells, was used for the transmittance measurements. All the pH measurements were carried out with a Cambridge pH meter (Bench Model).

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Standard metal and anions solutions: An osmium solution was prepared by dissolving osmic acid in cold distilled water or by dissolving potassium osmate in 0.1 (N) sodium hydroxide solution. The solution was stored in cold place and was standardised by precipitating the metal as sulphide, followed by ignition to the metal in hydrogen.

Weaker solutions were prepared by dilution of the stock solution with distilled water.

Other standard solutions of different metals, used to study the effect of diverse ions, were prepared by dissolving separately weighed amounts of the corresponding metal salts in distilled water or in dilute hydrochloric acid. Solutions of anions were prepared from the respective alkali metal salts.

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Reagent solutions: A 1% (w/v) solution of N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea (PBT) in 50% acetic acid was used for the precipitation of osmium. For spectrophotometric measurements, 0.01M, N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea in ethanol was used.

Gravimetric Determination of Osmium(VI)

Procedure: Dilute a known amount of osmium solution in a beaker to about 200 ml with distilled water. Warm the solution to about 60°-70° and add about 3-4 times the theoretical amount of 1% reagent solution in 50% acetic acid. Adjust the pH of the solution to 3.5-6.0 by adding dropwise 4(N) ammonia solution with constant stirring. Digest the dark green precipitate formed on a boiling water bath for about 1-2 hours with occasional stirring.

as OsO₂(C₁₁H₁₀N₂OS)₂. The conversion factor of the complex to metal is 0.2590.

Precision and accuracy: When this procedure was applied to the determination of 5.25 mg and 10.50 mg of osmium, the errors did not exceed 0.01 mg and 0.03 mg respectively. The standard deviation and relative mean error were found to be 0.47% and 0.16% respectively at the 10mg level (6 determinations).

Effect of acidity: The osmium(VI)-N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea complex begins to coagulate above pH 2.5, the optimum pH range for complete precipitation of the metal being 3.1-6.2. At lower pH, incomplete precipitation occurs.

Effect of reagent concentration: The precipitation of osmium(VI) with N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea (PBT) was complete when the supernatant liquid contained 0.315% (w/v) of the reagent in excess, the other conditions remaining the same.

Effect of diverse ions: Osmium(VI) was determined quantitatively with N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea (PBT) in a mixture containing known amounts of aluminium, nickel, cadmium, cobalt, titanium, chromium, zinc, manganese (as sulphate), mercury, iron, tin, barium, gold (as chloride), uranyl acetate, lead acetate, ammonium vanadate, ammonium molybdate, EDTA, fluoride or tartrate ions. The results are shown in Table-1.

It was possible to separate osmium from palladium, platinum, rhodium, iridium, or ruthenium by prior reduction of osmium(VIII/VI) by sulphur dioxide

TABLE-1 GRAVIMETRIC SEPARATION OF OSMIUM FROM DIVERSE IONS
Osmium taken=10.50 mg.

Foreign ion added (mg)	Os-found (mg)	Error (mg)	Foreign ion added (mg)	Os-found (mg)	Error (mg)
a 3+ Fe (100)	10.51	+0.01	c 3+ Ga (200)	10.48	-0.02
a 2+ Cu (100)	10.56	+0.06	c 3+ In (200)	10.51	+0.01
a 2+ Ni (100)	10.56	+0.06	c 3+ Ti (100)	10.48	-0.02
a 2+ Hg (100)	10.48	-0.02	c 3+ Al (200)	10.51	+0.01
a 3+ Au (100)	10.54	+0.04	c 6+ Mo (100)	10.48	-0.02
b 4+ Ti (200)	10.51	+0.01	c 6+ U (100)	10.54	-0.04
c 2+ Co (100)	10.54	+0.04	c 5+ V (100)	10.48	-0.02
c 2+ Zn (150)	10.48	-0.02	c 2+ Cd (100)	10.48	-0.02
c 2+ Mn (200)	10.48	-0.02			

a = In presence of EDTA
b = In presence of fluoride
c = In presence of tartrate

Wash the precipitate with hot 1% acetic acid solution and finally with hot water. Dry the complex at 110°-120° for 2 hours, cool in a desiccator and weigh

in 2(N) hydrochloric acid medium to osmium(IV). Osmium(IV) which was left behind in the filtrate after precipitation of the foreign metals with PBT,

could be oxidised to osmic acid with 5(N) nitric acid and distilled. The volatile osmium tetroxide was absorbed into 0.1N sodium hydroxide solution and the osmium content was then determined with PBT as described above.

Spectrophotometric Determination of Osmium(VI) :

Procedure : Place a measured amount of osmium metal solution in a 100-ml separatory funnel. Adjust the pH of the solution 3.5-5.0 with dilute hydrochloric acid and 10% sodium acetate solution. Shake the solution vigorously with an excess amount of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ ethanolic solution of N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea. Place the funnel over the boiling water bath for 10-15 minutes. Cool the solution to room temperature, add about 5 ml alcohol and 5 ml portions of chloroform and shake the separatory funnel with its contents well. Separate and dilute the green complex layer into a 25-ml volumetric flask with chloroform and measure the absorbance against appropriate reagent blank prepared under the same conditions with the same quantity of the reagent.

Results and Discussion

Properties of the metal complex : The osmium(VI)-N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea complex decomposes at 260°. It is stable in weakly acidic solution, soluble in alcohol and chloroform, partly soluble in benzene, isobutyl methyl ketone, carbon tetrachloride etc. The results of analysis of the pure complex, dried at 120° are as follows :

Found : Os=25.70%, N=11.50%, S=8.70%
 Required for $OsO_2(C_{13}H_{10}N_2OS)_2$: Os=25.74%,
 N=11.44%, S=8.72%

Absorbance curves : The absorbance curves of the solution of osmium(VI)-N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea complex in chloroform-ethanol mixture

showed two maxima, one at 345 nm and other at 600 nm. The curves are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 respectively.

Fig 2

Effect of pH : The acidity of osmium solution was adjusted with dilute hydrochloric acid and 10% sodium acetate solution. The pH values of the aqueous layers were measured after the extraction of the green metal complex. It was observed that 100% extraction of the metal ion could be made at pH 3.5-5.0.

Effect of reagent concentration : For complete extraction of the metal complex at the above pH, the reagent concentration was found to be 10.0 times that of the metal ion concentration.

Conformity of Beer's law and stability : In chloroform, the osmium(VI)-N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea complex obeyed Beer's law at 345 nm over the concentration range of $0.72 \mu g Os ml^{-1}$ to $2.8 \mu g Os ml^{-1}$ and at 650 nm over the concentration range of $5.76 \mu g Os ml^{-1}$ to $23.04 \mu g Os ml^{-1}$ respectively.

The colour of chloroform-ethanol extract was found to be stable for more than 24 hours. The molar absorptivities of the complexes are 31455 and 2500 at 345 nm and 650 nm respectively.

The sensitivities of the colour reactions are $0.0053 \mu g Os cm^{-2}$ and $0.0754 \mu g Os cm^{-2}$ at 345 nm and 650 nm respectively. The relative mean error and coefficient of variations were calculated at 650 nm and were found to be 0.25% and 0.84% respectively.

Effect of Diverse ions : Osmium was separated and determined in presence of diverse ions as described above. The tolerance limit for the foreign ions were

Fig 1

taken as the largest amounts in the presence of which the absorbance due to osmium was within 2% of the actual value. Large quantities of noble metals and base metals did not interfere in the determination of the metal. Only cyanide ions interfered. The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE—2 EFFECT OF FOREIGN IONS ON THE SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF OSMIUM(VI) AT 650 nm. (540.00 μg of osmium was used for each test)

Foreign ion added	Amount tolerated (μg)	Foreign ion	Amount added tolerated (μg)
a 4+ Ti	3000	c	UO ₂ 3000
b 2+ Ni	2500	c	6+ Mo 3000
b 2+ Cu	2500	c	5+ V5 1500
c 2+ Hg	2000	c	2+ Pb 3000
b 3+ Fe	2000		4+ Pt 2500
c 2+ Mn	3000		2+ Pd 2500
c 2+ Zn	3000		3+ Ir 2500
c 2+ Cd	3000		3+ Ru 1500
c 3+ Al	3000		3+ Rh 2500
c 3+ In	3000		3+ Au 3000
c 3+ Ga	3000		

a = In presence of fluoride
 b = In presence of EDTA
 c = In presence of tartrate

Nature of the complex : The empirical formula of the green osmium(VI)-N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea (PBT) complex was determined by mole-ratio method as described by Mayer and Ayres⁸. The results clearly indicated that a 1 : 2 metal-ligand complex was formed. The composition of the complex was verified by conventional Slope-ratio method. The dissociation constant of osmium(VI)-PBT complex was determined from mole-ratio curve⁹ and found to be 5.9×10^{-9} .

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